

Offshore and Tax Paradises

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“Dirty money has no place in our economy, whether it comes from drug deals, the illegal guns trade or trafficking in human beings. We must make sure that organised crime cannot launder its funds through the banking system or the gambling sector. Our banks should never function as Laundromats for mafia money, or enable the funding of terrorists.”

Cecilia Malmström, EU Home Affairs Commissioner, speaking about the Fourth EU Money Laundering Directive on 6 February 2013

Conceptual

It is a common opinion that one of the main and oldest sources of tax evasion at the international level is the use of tax havens.

The notion of a tax haven has only a relative value, since any country can be considered as a tax haven due to certain situations or particular operations. (Questions de fiscalité internationale, nº 1, l'évasion et la fraude fiscales internationales, quatre études, OECD).

For this reason, the identification of a tax haven is usually done through the verification of a set of generic requirements, although fundamental, namely:

- Low tax rates or complete absence of taxation;
- Existence of bank secrecy;
- Modern communication facilities;
- Lack of control over deposits by non-residents;
- Existence of a network of tax Conventions that establish the link between the tax haven and countries with strong fiscal pressure;
- Existence of political and economic stability;
- Advertising as an off-shore financial centre.

Some authors, such as Levine distinguish between tax havens and countries with low tax pressure, depending on whether or not the tax system has the sole objective of diverting international capital flows to its territory.

Tax havens, on the other hand, can be general or specialized, depending on whether they grant a favourable tax regime in relation to the generality of income or only in relation to certain specific categories.

Ways to use Tax Paradise

The use of tax havens can be carried out in a variety of ways, with emphasis on the importance of manipulating operations between companies belonging to the same group and the creation of base companies or intermediate companies.

In the first case, taking advantage of the existence of dependency relations, the taxable matter is relocated to countries where the fiscal pressure is more reduced or null.

The expedient generally used is to increase the income of companies located in countries where the rates are lower, reducing them, consequently, those in countries with high taxation.

The main instruments used are the establishment of transfer prices, loans and remuneration for services, among others.

The transfer pricing stipulation constitutes a very common practice of international tax evasion that consists of transmitting goods and services at an artificially low price.

A non-independent person who, for whatever reason, escapes to tax, or to acquire goods under the same conditions at an artificially high price.

If, for example, a company is established in a state with a low level of taxation and its subsidiary in another country with high tax rates, the latter sells its goods at a low price, in order to have a reduced benefit or null, while the parent company subsequently resells them at the normal price, thus achieving a high income that will be subject to reduced taxation, under the regime in force in its country of establishment.

Such a procedure can be used by granting loans to a company in the same group.

Thus, as Louis Cartou mentions if a company lends to a certain amount, the establishment of an artificially high interest rate allows the debtor company, which is established in a country with high tax rates, to reduce the taxable profit.

Instead, if she is in a country with reduced tax rates, stipulating a low interest rate allows her to increase the tax base, which will be subject to reduced taxation.

Finally, it will be said that the transfer of benefits can also be achieved by other means, namely through the payment of services provided or the imposition, to each company of a certain group, of the common costs that were borne.

With regard to the creation of companies in tax havens, the problem is even more relevant, given the increased difficulty in controlling such situations.

Basic companies aim to reduce the tax burden in the country of residence of the persons who control it.

They are generally constituted with the objective of receiving the income that would, in his absence, be received directly by the taxpayer, thus escaping taxation in his State of residence.

The existence of its own legal personality causes income to fall within its legal sphere, thus escaping the rule of the principle of universality applicable to residents of a given fiscal space.

In most cases, there is a complete absence of taxation or insignificant taxation in the State in which the company is established.

Strictly speaking, the use of these companies should not lead to more than a deferral in taxation, however, this is not the case, since the partners always have the option of not distributing the income or of using other strategies so that they remain permanently away from taxation.

They can, for example, distribute them in the form of wages, loans, under a double taxation convention, or, quite simply, sell their participation in order to benefit from an exempt or taxed surplus value to a lower rate.

Basic companies can be classified according to the activity they perform in asset management companies, operating companies, operating in commerce or industry, or financial companies, among others.

A typical example of common societies is that of the so-called "rent a star", in which an artist is employed by a certain society, of which he is the owner, established in a tax haven.

The said company receives income from his professional activity and he, who is domiciled in a country with high tax rates, simply receives a salary.

Intermediary companies, on the other hand, are entities incorporated in a given State with the objective of taking advantage of the taxation regime provided for in a given tax Convention.

This mechanism, commonly known as "treaty shopping", normally presupposes a comparative examination of the advantages that are granted in the various conventions to avoid double taxation and the choice of the most favourable, after which the evader inserts himself artificially in his prediction, thus benefiting from the advantages that were not intended for him.

There are fundamentally and following, two types of strategies through which one can practice the “hunt for treaties”, which are the following:

- Direct pass: Country A has entered into a tax convention with country B that grants individuals and companies resident in B exemption from withholding tax for income they earn in A. One resident in country C, with which there is no convention, may become a company in B where it transfers assets and rights that generate dividends, interest or royalties in A, the payment of which to that company escapes taxation. Subsequently, taking advantage of tax benefits, this company can relay the income to C.
- Passage in jump: A company resident in country C earns income in country A without any agreement between the two states to eliminate double taxation. Country B, however, has a convention with A that grants exemption from withholding tax at A to income earned by residents in B and, in turn, although it has high fiscal pressure, widely accepts consistent deductions on income paid to foreign entities. Country D, where the tax pressure is low, has entered into an agreement with C that attributes benefits to the income earned in its territory by residents in C. The way to escape taxation in country A is to create a company in B, which receives the income paid by residents of A. Subsequently, the company established in B makes payments to a company resident in D, which in turn transfers them to the company established in C.

The misuse of the agreements can also be made through the creation of companies that comply with the minimum requirements for participation in the capital, as a way to guarantee the maintenance of the conventional provisions to the income subject to distribution.

Offshore banking and Organized Crime

The end of borders, in the case of the countries that joined the EU, as well as the absolute lack of political and military control over the extensive territory of the former USSR, opened a corridor, from the Baltic Sea to the Pacific, for the flow of products from organizations such as the Sicilian Mafia (Cosa Nostra), the Russian Mafia, the Chinese Triads, the Yakuza (Japanese) and the Colombian Cartels.

This movement, on a planetary scale, involved agreements and understandings, taking into account a "banking support" already prepared in the "tax havens", and prospered in the financial markets, under the mark of three circumstances:

- a) The fall in profitability in traditional productive businesses;
- b) The excess of dollars resulting from the existence of increasing payments deficit and domestic debt in the USA, for at least 50 years, to the same extent that the dollar assumed the condition of world currency.

c) The process of privatization of the economy of the former USSR, in the 1990s, under the government of Boris Yeltsin, through which Russian mafias came to dominate 70% of the financial system of the Russian Federation, according to data from ZIEGLER (2001) .

Holders of available, liquid capital, the Russian mafias have opened an extremely important "gateway" to the global financial system.

The intersection with the globalized activity of organized crime, in its less shocking version, occurred in successive fraud operations on balance sheets and accounts. In two other aspects, the phenomenon can also be noticed: in the implementation of an e-commerce system, based on Internet operations and in the privatization of international postal services - in which the main company is FEDEX, based in the USA.

In this macro-context there are other elements to be considered: the issue of patents and the control of biodiversity - a struggle waged from behind the scenes of international diplomacy to the ends of the Amazon.

In the shadow of the state, criminal agents operate a bio piracy policy strongly linked to the worlds of organized crime.

From a geopolitical point of view, Miami and Los Angeles (USA) appear as strategic "capitals" of organized crime for Latin America, Europe, Africa and Asia, especially in the two most relevant aspects: drug and arms trafficking.

Not by chance, and the data are from the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United States appears as the leader in the ranking of "washers". It is Jean François Thony, former Legal Director of the IMF who says: "Among the countries that launder the most money are the USA, where 50% of all financial operations are carried out that are based on drug trafficking, terrorism, kidnapping, smuggling, corruption and other illegal activities.

The different networks and worldwide connections, which operate with the support of ultra-technology, escape, even for now, from the reach of the so-called Financial Intelligence Units (FIU) - Financial Intelligence Unit), which act worldwide in the so-called Egmont Group. In its latest report, the Group notes: the delay in money laundering investigations means that few configurations involving new technologies or techniques have been presented - such as laundering via the Internet, smart cards (smart cards) or online banking.

Over the years, more and more cases involving these technologies will come to the attention of crime repression forces (COAF, org., 2001, p. 13). The available literature on organized crime is only now beginning to bring together cases of laundering "dirty" capital based on high tech schemes. As electronic money grows in terms of volume in

transactions in the real economy, more and more organized crime moves through the networks and nodes of the immense network of virtual money.

Precisely in this dimension, there are difficulties in identifying the "dirty capital", obtained from the sale of drugs and weapons, for example, which is "washed" daily and receives the blessings of the market, invading the economies of the central countries of capitalism, as well as emerging calls, without being disturbed by anyone.

Money laundering is presented as an activity, that is, carrying out acts concatenated in time and space, with a view to achieving a determined goal. Those linked actions are concealment, concealment and integration.

From the point of view of the strategic action of organized crime, concealment and concealment are antecedent movements to integration action, when "dirty money" re-enters the economy in the form of lawful market investments. At this stage, it will rarely be possible to recover the assets generated by the activities

The themes of organized crime and money laundering always appear so interconnected that it seems impossible to write about one without analyzing the other.

A fundamental part of the strategy of criminal organizations, laundering is always a delicate moment that exposes the illegality of the resources handled to authorities and public agents.

As the volume of illicit business reached and exceeded the billions of dollars a year, this mountain of capital could not be washed away as it was in the days of Al Capone. The term laundering came about when the American mafia invested in laundries (and other small businesses) to legalize the money earned from the sale of illegal products and services in the 1920s United States - mainly alcoholic beverages and high-level prostitution.

The so-called "money laundering", or concealment of assets, right and values derived from crimes, today constitutes a complex and changing process socio-economic situation, which occurs in almost all the nations of the world, valuation in a normative standard are recent (the first legislation incriminating specifically this practice dates from the late 1980s).

In the sophistication of the "washing" schemes, two aspects stand out: the use of tax havens and the intense use of information technology - network, online or cable communication -, aiming to escape any attempts at international or state control. In other words, it is possible to state that:

a) Although banks in Switzerland and other countries have traditionally provided financial services without asking their customers much, havens have not existed for

half a century on a scale comparable to now. They proliferated when the American government, in 1963, limited loans from domestic banks to foreign customers, and in 1968 President Lyndon Johnson tried to compel companies with foreign subsidiaries to repatriate their profits quickly. The effect of these measures was fantastic.

The 375 branches of 26 American banks that existed in 1968, with a turnover of US \$ 22 billion, multiplied in 1971 to more than a thousand branches of 79 banks, with assets of US \$ 52 billion.

b) It was from the 1980s, with the expansion of telephony and, later, of the Internet, that the conditions of communication were created, capable of allowing the acceleration of traffic without frontiers of money, virtual currency, binary digit that, in principle, it does not correspond to anything that exists in the world and accumulates in a few backwaters around the Earth, always needing to circulate and return with a little more profit.

The portentous network of tax havens had already been established. In relation to tax havens, it is important to clarify an issue: the modern architecture of the network of tax havens, which became an immense global laundry during the after the Cold War, is the result of a state policy, commanded by the USA.

The State Department (US) and the Treasury approached the country's main international banks with a proposal to do something they would have feared doing without official encouragement.

They were to establish and expand their own agencies in the world's large volatile capital centres - and perhaps help establish some new ones.

This would not only attract volatile foreign money, but would also maintain the substantial amounts that were being sent abroad by American tax evaders. Chase and other major American banks responded by setting up a network of offshore centres to convert the United States into a high-profile Switzerland.

Economist Michael Hudson professor at the University of Missouri (Kansas, USA), further maintains: "the US government and the banks were well aware of the fact that offenders are the most liquid people in the world, simple reason that they fear owning property in full view of the authorities.

The exception to this rule mentioned by HUDSON seems to be the case of properties "washed" through a tangle of front companies and "oranges", under the baton of law firms specialized in the administration of this type of business.

This fact, of origin, contributes to explain the estimates of (2005), which place the USA as the main origin and destination of the flow of dirty money in the world.

The number one position in the ranking of money laundering countries, on the part of the United States, tends to cover the issue of organized crime as an inseparable part of American geopolitics in the post-fall scenario of the Berlin Wall.

Money laundering involves a sequence of acts in time and space: concealment, concealment and integration of resources or placement (conversion) to concealment.

- The first step in a classic washing process is therefore called conversion or concealment. The “washer” seeks to hide the illicit origin of its assets, with a view to physically, politically and economically separating the operator of corporate organized crime from the one who obtained the additional resources in a previous criminal operation.

The washing operation known as smurfing (allocation of resources in small batches or in the form of merchandise, for the purpose of smuggling) is possibly the most typical example of that first chain action, once used as a tactic to escape the limits imposed by laws .

- The second step is concealment. Once capital has been concealed or converted, it is now a matter of making it appear legitimate: "disguise the illicit origin and make it difficult for state agencies to control and repress the paper trail."

Thus, illicit assets they are diluted in many accounts and statements, in different companies and countries. Hotels, motels, schools, churches and charities that live on donations, in short, any sector in which it is difficult to measure revenue, lends itself to dissimulation.

The author emphasizes that this stage "embodies the actual washing, that is, aims to provide etiologically illicit assets with a disguise of legitimacy."

A feature widely used by professional “washers” is the use of the “cable transfer” system. The data collected by STERLING (1997, p. 223), referring to the 1990s, speak for themselves: A trillion and a half dollars a day, legal and illegal, enter and leave the United States only, by electronic wire transfer. One hundred billion annually changes hands in the United States' drug market, and 500 billion worldwide.

On the other hand, in the times of Internet and global connections, in real time, washing schemes called clandestine laundries still exist, that is, those schemes whose requirement base does not require American Express moneygrams or an accomplice financial institution.

The author writes: Huge sums of money are transferred from one end of the map to the other, through the ancient hawala system in Asia, based on a phone call, a card or a fax. A brief message from London produces money on paper or gold in Lahore, without going through the monetary system at all. Asian immigrants send remittances

to families in this way; Asian drug dealers launder money through the same channels. Together, they move between 10 and 20 billion dollars a year, totally on the basis of trust (STERLING, 1997, p. 227).

- The final step in the washing scheme is integration. As the expression suggests, it is a matter of enabling the apparently legitimate use of goods or values “in the productive system, through the creation, acquisition and / or investment in lawful businesses or by the simple purchase of goods: The financial and real estate markets, auctions of rare arts and objects are some of the sectors preferred by washers.

Sterling (1997, p. 231) reinforces the sine qua non condition that money laundering represents for the reproduction of capital generated by organized crime. The author recommends: Discovering and taking criminal money means making the act of laundering a crime; pick it up at the point of entry into the banking system; track it through the system since entry and on its reinvestment in some legal company; identify the mover; identify the owner behind the mover; identify the source of the money; resort to legal instruments to seize the money and arrest the owner as well as the mover; ensure investigations, seizures and arrests across national borders; and do all of this without violating the individual's legitimate right to privacy.

Conclusion

All the corruption schemes involving bankers and politicians (or their family) have a team working in that cell and money laundry scheme. All of them are responsible to accomplish the final purpose: Introduce in the legal economy “dirty money”. This is an economic crime and all the team is part of a small or big organized crime – even the bankers and its personnel.

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